

Section 1: Applicants

Name of the main applicant	Adam Kewley
Affiliation – institution	Technische Universiteit Delft
Affiliation – department	BioMechanical Engineering
Position	Open-Source Developer
End date of contract	permanent position
Guarantee needed & added yes/no/n.a.	n.a.
E-mail address	a.kewley@tudelft.nl
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Name of the co-applicant	Ajay Seth
Affiliation – institution	Technische Universiteit Delft
Affiliation – department	BioMechanical Engineering
Position	Associate Professor
End date of contract	permanent position
Guarantee added yes/no/n.a.	n.a.
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Section 2: Summary

Proposed project title	<i>OPynSim: A python-native library for interoperable biomechanical simulations</i>
Project duration (in months)	24 months

English public summary

Word count EN-SUM (max 100): OpenSim is the most popular simulator for biomechanical research in the world. While free and open-source software, it does not integrate easily with the Python ecosystem, which is rapidly becoming the de facto standard for Open Science. Our goal is to make OpenSim's integration as seamless as possible by designing, developing, and documenting "Python-native" bindings for OpenSim that focus on ease-of-use, performance, teachability, and interoperability. This will be paired with the development of a standardized "study" file format, which will provide the community with a clear way to interchange the library's models, input data, and analysis results.

Dutch public summary

Word count NL-SUM (max 100): OpenSim is de populairste simulator voor biomechanisch onderzoek wereldwijd. Hoewel het gratis en open-source is, integreert het niet gemakkelijk met het snelgroeiende Python-ecosysteem, dat steeds meer de standaard wordt binnen Open Science. Ons doel is om de integratie met Python te vereenvoudigen door het ontwikkelen van gebruiksvriendelijke, prestatiegerichte en goed gedocumenteerde "Python-native" koppelingen voor OpenSim. Daarnaast werken we aan een gestandaardiseerd "studie"-bestandsformaat, waarmee onderzoekers modellen, invoergegevens en analyseresultaten eenvoudig kunnen uitwisselen binnen de gemeenschap.

Section 3: Alignment with the scope of the call

3.1 Vision for the project and alignment with the aim of this call

Word count SEC31 (max. 150): Our vision is to make Open Science the most natural choice for industry professionals, researchers, and educators. To achieve that, we propose building on OpenSim's Open Science principles by implementing "python native" bindings to OpenSim's C++ API, called OPynSim, and a standardized "study file format", called osimstud, for the OpenSim ecosystem. OPynSim will make OpenSim a first-class citizen in the wider python ecosystem, which is rapidly becoming the de facto standard for science, industry, and education. The osimstud file format will make interchanging musculoskeletal studies easier and therefore will be key infrastructure for making study data FAIR. Teachability will be major focus of the design, with the specific intent of making OpenSim accessible to new users. This strongly aligns with a wider trend of Dutch universities adopting python as the Open Science lingua franca of science, technology, engineering, and maths.

3.2 User communities, challenges and needs

Word count SEC32 (max. 200): OpenSim's existing python infrastructure is not "python native"; instead, it uses an automatic process to generate its python API from its C++ API. This directly exposes users to a C++-style API, which creates significant friction. Concretely, whenever a user (e.g. student, prosthetic designer, zoologist, roboticist, computer scientist) wants to use OpenSim, they need to explore its C++ documentation, understand its vast API, and write interoperability layers around it to deliver value in their work. Therefore, OPynSim will provide a crucial piece of infrastructure that will connect OpenSim's existing community (>850k downloads¹, >3500 seminal paper citations²) to the python ecosystem and aid its expansion into new disciplines (e.g. comparative biology, neuroscience, human-robot interaction) by making it more teachable, accessible, and interoperable.

Although OpenSim already provides a standardized model definition file (.osim), biomechanical studies typically require aggregating model definition files with a variety of other data files (e.g. meshes, motion capture recordings, EMG/IMU data, force plate readings, CT scans). The resulting aggregate, its metadata, and the various relationships between the constituent files, is not standardized. This makes it challenging for users, library personnel, information managers, and platform developers to make biomechanical studies FAIR.

3.3 Alignment of project with OS principles

Word count SEC33 (max. 200): OpenSim is a permissively licensed library with a successful OS heritage. We propose continuing that heritage by using open protocols and techniques to build OPynSim, which will be an open-source, permissively licensed, python library infrastructure around OpenSim's existing C++ API. We will design OPynSim to be easy to teach, interoperable with the wider python ecosystem, and locally installed on user's computers. This will ensure that OpenSim's algorithms can be used on a variety of computers, rather than being reliant on platforms provided by externally governed entities that may not align with OS principles. The software will be developed in the open with a transparent, collaborative, development methodology.

The osimstud file format will be developed as an open community-based standard and provide an open-source reference implementation, so that the entire community can benefit from a flexible and interoperable study file format. This will make the research datasets produced by OPynSim FAIRer and makes osimstud the Open Science data complement to OPynSim's open-source code.

Section 4: Feasibility

4.1 Project plan

Word count SEC41 (max. 750): Our plan is to deliver five work packages; each one is designed as a milestone that enhances the OpenSim ecosystem:

- **WPA1**: set up and announce a minimum viable product (MVP) version of OPynSim. We will set up a landing page, public repository, continuous integration pipeline, and deployment targets for OPynSim. Minimum viability will be achieved by including some easy-to-implement—but useful—functions/classes in the initial release.
- **WPA2** (depends on **WPA1**): establish and develop OPynSim's core features so that they can be used successfully in at least one published project or course. We will directly collaborate with users to establish the features they need. Those features will be developed using a continuous delivery methodology that gets new versions of OPynSim in the users' hands as quickly as possible.
- **WPB1**: add “virtual filesystem (VFS)” support to the core OpenSim C++ codebase. We will update the core OpenSim C++ codebase so that it can load model definition files and associated data via an abstract interface. This will enable OpenSim to load data from a wide variety of backing stores; for example, an unstructured directory layout (current behaviour), a structured study file archive (**WPB2**), or a database.
- **WPB2** (depends on **WPB1**): specify and implement the osimstud file format. We will collaborate with the OpenSim community and users to establish requirements. Additionally, we will study existing study data (e.g. from <https://simtk.org>) to understand any common practises that could be included in the osimstud specification. We will then openly publish a high-level description of our proposed osimstud format and iterate on it with the community until a consensus is established. Finally, we will implement, document, and test a reference implementation that can handle a representative set of osimstud files.
- **WPC1** (depends on **WPA1** and **WPB2**): implement first-class support for the osimstud format in OPynSim. This will enable users to create and manipulate osimstud files via their own python scripts, which is a key prerequisite for building FAIR systems (e.g. study repositories, metadata search tools).

Our 24-month roadmap to deliver the work packages is as follows:

1. Months 1-3: setup and announce WPA1. So that the community is made aware of OPynSim and able to use its MVP functionality early in the project.
2. Months 2-12: iterate WPA1 towards WPA2. Use **WPA1** to drive community engagement in the development process. Develop all aspects of OPynSim (bindings, tests, documentation, examples). Identify projects/courses that want to directly collaborate on the development of **WPA2**.
3. Months 12-24: ensure WPA2's features are useful by integrating them into active research projects/courses. Use the challenges presented by actual projects/courses to ensure **WPA2** has enough features to deliver real value. That value is a key deliverable of this project.
4. Months 2-6: design and implement WPB1. Work with the core OpenSim team to implement VFS support in the core OpenSim C++ codebase.
5. Months 2-12: design and implement WPB2 and WPC1. Release an open specification draft alongside a reference implementation that the community can engage with. This may overlap with **WPB1**'s design and **WPA2** (the reference implementation may be developed in OpenSim's core C++ codebase or **WPC1**).
6. Months 12-24: seed usage of the osimstud format to grow its impact. Manually port popular existing (unstructured) study data to the osimstud format. This is to directly show the community why they should want to use osimstud's FAIRer file format (e.g. because it is easier to list and extract datasets from an osimstud file).

These work packages, and the timeline, are designed to initially ship smaller deliverables and then iterate on them in conjunction with direct community/project/course engagement. This minimizes the risk of overruns while

maximizing the effectiveness of engagement. Additionally, the work packages are also timed, split, and parallelized along expertise and dependency lines to minimize risk:

- **WPA1/WPA2** form a standalone workstream that is most likely to be limited by internal development resources. **WPA1** requires strong development expertise for a short time, **WPA2** can be serviced by a wider variety of skillsets over a longer time.
- **WPB1/WPB2** form a standalone workstream that is likely to be limited by communication, consensus, and synchronization with the OpenSim community. The impact of those limitations will be minimized by developing **WPA1/WPA2** in parallel.
- **WPC1** is where the **WPA/WPB** workstreams join (it is dependent on them), but **WPC1**'s risk can be minimized by making **WPB2**'s reference implementation usable by, or part of, **WPC1**'s development.

4.2 Team composition

Name, surname	Affiliation	Expertise	Role/contributions
<i>Dr. A. (Adam) Kewley</i>	<i>TUD</i>	<i>Research software development.</i>	<i>Project manager, implementor</i>
<i>Dr. A. (Ajay) Seth</i>	<i>TUD</i>	<i>Musculoskeletal modelling, academic and industrial applications of OpenSim.</i>	<i>Expert knowledge, community</i>
	<i>TUD</i>	<i>Teaching/education, high-level python software development.</i>	<i>Using OPynSim in a project or course. Writing documentation and examples. Developing high-level python functionality.</i>

Word count SEC42 (max. 350): Adam Kewley is a senior open-source software developer in the Biomechanical Engineering department at TU Delft. His previous experience includes implementing high-throughput research automation systems (Unilever Ltd.), engineering big data systems in astronomy (Gaia Satellite, University of Cambridge), and engineering low-level genomic data compression systems (Petagene Ltd.). In his current role, he has worked directly in the OpenSim community, making many changes to OpenSim's core architecture to improve performance, reliability, and utility while providing direct development support to active research projects. He is the lead designer, developer, and maintainer of OpenSim Creator³, a large C++ UI project that directly integrates against the OpenSim core API. OpenSim Creator's development approach (MVP, rapid iteration with community feedback) mirrors our proposal for this project. Adam Kewley will be the lead developer and manager of this project.

Ajay Seth is an associate professor of musculoskeletal modelling in the Biomechanical Engineering department at TU Delft. Previously, he was the architect and developer of the OpenSim core API at Stanford University for nearly a decade. He leads the Computational Biomechanics Lab at TU Delft, which focuses on developing computational solutions that use OpenSim to manage human-machine interaction, design prosthetics, and study human/animal movement. He has deep expertise in how OpenSim currently works, why its features are necessary to accurately model biomechanical systems, and what it will likely need in the future. His persistent role in the OpenSim community, and knowledge of current/upcoming projects in that community, will provide a ripe source of design and development opportunities in this project.

The third, still to be hired/contracted, member should have some familiarity with python programming or technical writing. **WPA2** will involve a mixture of tasks, some of them (e.g. low-level C++ engineering) can be fulfilled by Adam Kewley, but others (e.g. python development, documentation, tutorial writing, scripting interesting examples) are small standalone tasks that could be fulfilled by a less experienced team member on a short-term or part-time basis.

4.3 Risk management

Risk	Likelihood and impact	Risk mitigation strategy
Over-scoping/overruns	Likelihood: medium Impact: low-medium	Work packages with short timelines and iterative delivery.
Community Engagement	Likelihood: low Impact: high	Team composition, interoperability with existing projects.

Upstream/external development delays	Likelihood: low-medium Impact: medium	Standalone work streams, alternative strategies for delivering WPB1/WPB2/WPC1 .
Platform/hosting outages	Likelihood: low Impact: high (short-term), low (long-term)	Work packages are designed to be platform-independent and run locally. No deliverables depend on a specialized live service and can be redundantly hosted on GitHub (US), Zenodo (EU), and TU Delft's GitLab instance (NL).
Third-party library breakages, deletions, end-of-life.	Likelihood: low/medium Impact: medium/high	Work packages are designed to minimize third-party dependencies and be installable without being dependent on a specific package manager (e.g. conda).

Word count SEC43 (max. 150): The most common risks in software projects are over-scoping, which can lead to overruns; synchronization/engagement with external teams, which can stall developers while they wait for decisions/reviews; and external changes to platform/library dependencies, which can stall, or entirely reverse, development progress. Our project plan is designed to manage those risks.

All work packages focus on delivering things early and iterating on them, rather than relying on a long up-front design phase. The OPynSim work packages (**WPA1/WPA2**) will be developed independently of the upstream OpenSim team, and suitable projects/courses are already available in TUD for integration and community feedback (**WPA2**).

WPB1/WPB2/WPC1 require external collaboration, but they can be worked on in parallel with **WPA1/WPA2**, minimizing the impact of communication stalls. Additionally, **WPB2** and **WPC1** can be delivered without **WPB1** by rescopeing the work to develop a shim layer that unpacks osimstud files into a backwards-compatible temporary directory that can be opened with an unmodified (i.e. without **WPB1**) OpenSim.

4.4 Budget

Position	HOT scale	Institution	Total FTE	Years active	Amount
Research Software Engineer (Adam Kewley)	HOT 2.1 - 13	TUD	1,60	2	€ 212.464,00
Teaching Assistant (to be hired/contracted)	HOT 2.1 - 10	TUD	0,20	2	€ 17.615,00

Material/IT Type	Description	Cost calculation	Total (€)
(international) travel and accommodation expenses incl. conference visit	Attendance of team members to one international conference per year and one or two smaller national conferences/symposiums within NL	(1,000 per international conference x 2 yr x 2p) + (250 per national event x 2 x 2 yr x 2p)	€ 6.000,00

Total Personnel requested: 230.079,00

Total Material/IT requested: 6.000,00

Total budget requested: 236.079,00

4.5 Budget justification

Word count SEC 45 (max. 200): Most of the budget is allocated toward 0.8 FTE of Adam Kewley's position (1 FTE), so that he can dedicate most of his attention to the project for its two-year duration. The unallocated remainder of his

position (0.2 FTE) is not specified by this proposal but is likely to be allocated to strongly related projects (e.g. maintaining OpenSim Creator³, supporting academic projects that use OpenSim).

The work that will be assigned to the third (still to be hired/contracted) 0.1 FTE team member will be specifically designed as small standalone tasks that will be suitable for a junior research software engineer or teaching/educational assistant (tutorial writer, technical writer, example designer) who can work on the project short-term or part-time without requiring extensive initial training.

The travel budget will be used on sending team members to meetings, conferences, and symposiums so that they can directly engage with the wider community, advertise this project, and advertise (their use-case of) its work packages. We envision attending one or two international conferences during the project but will prefer national symposiums/conferences because they will be a cost-effective way to build collaborations within NL.

4.6 Impact plan

Word count SEC46 (max. 200): OPynSim (**WPA1/WPA2**) will dramatically improve the utility of musculoskeletal modelling for these key demographics:

- **Students, hobbyists, individuals:** A significant part of **WPA2** is focused on writing clear, easy-to-follow open-access documentation and examples. A key milestone will be OPynSim's use in a course at TUD.
- **Researchers:** We plan on directly collaborating with community research projects during the development of **WPA2**. Our impact metric will be OPynSim's or osimstud's use in published works.
- **Businesses:** We plan on collaborating with suitable businesses (e.g. Model Health⁴) to establish what their specific needs are. Our impact metric will OPynSim's or osimstud's use by those businesses.

The osimstud format (**WBP1/WBP2/WPC1**) will make it easier for the community to exchange FAIR data. Our impact metric will be to measure how many new studies use the osimstud format - especially those publish new science derived from aggregations of many osimstud files.

At a high-level, the impact of OPynSim will be roughly measured using download counters and counting how many projects/packages list the OPynSim package as dependency. Additionally, we will measure OpenSim's impact statistics (citations, downloads, etc.) as an indirect metric of the impact of federating our development as part of OpenSim's wider ecosystem.

Section 5: Sustainability and software management

Section 5.1: Sustainability plan

Word count SEC51 (max 300): There is a large difference in sustainability between software that requires long-term maintenance to work at all (e.g. live services, libraries/applications with many rapidly changing external dependencies) and software that will continue to work with very little maintenance over many years. Our plan focuses on delivering the latter, because we envision that OPynSim/osimstud will be used many years after the project timeline.

To maintain their end-of-project functionality, the work packages have these long-term sustainability requirements:

- Hosting for the source code, specification documents, and documentation (cheap/free, widely available).
- Package hosting for the python packages (e.g. PyPi, conda – cheap/free, widely available).
- Updates to any C++ code when operating systems are updated (C++ is strongly backwards compatible).
- Updates to the python code when python is updated (python3 is strongly backwards compatible).
- Updates to the C++/python code whenever a dependency is updated (discussed below).

None of the above requirements depend on specialized knowledge from a specific individual to sustain the work, and all work packages will be developed using open-source/free tools and platforms. The last point is addressed through strict dependency management: OPynSim will only use a limited number of proven, stable, python dependencies that do not have transitive dependencies (e.g. numpy), or use dependencies over which we have direct control and expertise (e.g. OpenSim).

Our primary sustainability concern is in establishing how the project can grow beyond its end-of-project functionality. This is where community building, integration into courses, application in research projects, and usage in businesses is paramount and is a major reason why our work packages are designed to deliver something quickly: it lets us spend most of the project's time growing a community around the products.

Section 5.2: Software management plan

1. Please provide a brief description of your software, stating its purpose and intended audience.

We will develop three software deliverables:

- OPynSim: Python bindings to the OpenSim core C++ codebase (WPA1/WPA2). Will provide a “python-native” (or, “pythonic”) API to OpenSim, which is a well-established C++ library. Intended for use by most users in our target demographics (teaching, research, business).
- Virtual filesystem (VFS) support within the existing the OpenSim core C++ codebase (WPB1). Will enable OpenSim to load its model definition and associated data files (meshes, motion recordings, etc.) via an abstract interface that could be backed by a directory (legacy behaviour), structured study file (WPB2), or any other data service (e.g. a database). Intended for use by experienced C++ developers in the OpenSim community.
- A reference implementation of a study file reader (WPB2/WPC1). Will provide the community with an API for reading and manipulating our proposed study file format. The high-level parts of the reference implementation are intended for use by most users, the low-level parts are intended for use by experienced python/C++ system builders.

2. How will you manage versioning of your software?

All software will be versioned using git, including in-development versions. Formal release versions of the software (tested, documented, release notes/binaries/documentation deployed) will be tagged in git. The version-controlled git repository will be centrally hosted on GitHub (US). As part of the project's versioned release process, each release

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will also be deployed to Zenodo (EU) and the GitHub repository will be mirrored to TU Delft's GitLab instance (NL), so that the project outputs are not dependent on a single hosting supplier or country.

3. How will you make your software publicly available? What licence will your software have?

All software outputs will be developed in a public git repository, available on GitHub. To exercise the public release process (explained above), we will also release early alpha builds (tagged as such), so that redundant copies of the work are also publicly available on other systems (Zenodo, TUD GitLab, PyPi).

All software will be licensed with the Apache License (version 2.0, <https://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0>). This is an OSI-approved permissive license. OpenSim and OpenSim Creator, which are related projects, use the same license. All third-party dependencies (incl. transitive dependencies) will be vetted by our team to ensure compatibility with that license.

4. How will users of your software be able to cite your software?

Pre-production, we plan on publishing a short one-page article that describes the intention of this project to an open access journal or a preprint platform. This will provide users with a citeable resource early in the project.

During production, we plan on publishing all formal releases (incl. alpha releases) of the software to Zenodo.org. This will provide users with a way to cite exactly which version of the software they used. The git repositories will link these versioned releases in its README.md, CITATION.cff, and codemeta.json entries, which are de facto standard ways to communicate this information.

Later in the production process, we plan on writing a comprehensive article that summarizes the software's utility, architecture, and real-world use-cases. This will provide users with a citeable resource that explains the software in a version-independent way and will supersede the pre-production planning article.

5. How will your software be documented? Please describe your plans for: user documentation, documentation for future developers and for installation requirements. Please provide links to documentation if already available.

The project's landing page will direct users to the git repository and user documentation. The git repository will contain a README.md file (a de facto standard) that contains high-level project documentation. This top-level documentation will contain a high-level explanation of the project, its use-cases, funding acknowledgement, and will link to more specific documentation pages.

User documentation will be written in Sphinx, which is a standard open-source tool for generating technical documentation. In the case of OPynSim, user documentation also includes python API documentation. The generated documentation pages will be uploaded to a suitable webserver and links to it will be provided from the project's landing page and README.md file.

All varieties of installation methods (build from source, install a python package from a local directory, install using a package manager) will be included in the user documentation. If a common installation method is short and easy-to-understand (e.g. a single command in a terminal) then it will also be documented in the README.md file.

Documentation intended for future developers who want to modify the internals of the software will also be exposed via the user documentation, but in a clearly marked "for developers" section. This documentation will outline the project's architecture, how to build it, any governance concerns (PRs, reviews, style guides, etc.).

Both the public API and any internal APIs will be documented with comments or docstrings in the source files, where appropriate.

6. How will contribution guidelines and governance structure of your software be documented?

The software will provide a combination of CONTRIBUTING.md/CODE_OF_CONDUCT.md files (de facto standards), and/or there will be a clearly marked contribution/governance entry in the "for developers" section of the user documentation. These documents will outline how contributions should be structured for the project and will provide the community with something they can cite in the case of disputes.

7. How will your software be tested?

Using a layered testing approach. We will combine automated unit tests (low-level), integration tests (mid-level) and system tests (high-level) with manual exploratory testing (i.e. manually trying things out, followed by adding an automated test when it doesn't work).

Precisely which combination of technologies are used will depend on which (part of the) software is being tested. For OPynSim (**WPA1/WPA2**), we will likely use pytest/unittest (common python testing libraries) to test any python code and googletest/catch2 (common C++ testing libraries) to test the underlying C++ code. Adding VFS support to OpenSim (**WPB1**) will involve adding new tests to OpenSim's existing Catch2 C++ test suite. The reference implementation of a study file reader (**WPB2/WPC1**) will depend on which language it is ultimately implemented in, but the test suite will likely exercise the implementation by feeding test fixture osimstud files into the reference implementation.

In all cases, a top-level build system/script will be responsible for ensuring that all test suites are combined and ran as part of the release process. Additionally, the release process will include some amount of manual exploratory testing, and an automated test will be added whenever this manual process reveals an issue. Issues reported by users will be verified and, where appropriate, their use-case will be added to the test suite as a regression test.

8. How will you check that it respects the licences of libraries and dependencies it uses?

All dependencies, including transitive dependencies, will be vetted to ensure they use a license that is compatible with our chosen license. Additionally, we will intermittently vet if any third-party libraries have changed their license during the project. Where possible, the version of a library dependency will be “pinned”, so that vetting can also be performed during a manual library upgrade procedure. We have already vetted the libraries we plan to use (OpenSim, OpenSim’s transitive dependencies, numpy, nanobind, pandas) and confirmed that they currently have licenses that are compatible with our chosen license.

Notably, our project plan includes strictly limiting the number of (and depth of) third-party dependencies that our software uses. This is because our software is intended to be installed on user's machines and integrated by the user – potentially with a wide variety of other libraries. Dependency collisions and poor dependency control would undermine this goal and make it challenging for users to ensure their projects respect their chosen license.

9. How will your software be packaged and distributed?

OPynSim (**WPA1/WPA2**) will be built into standalone binary wheels for each target architecture (x86_64, amd64) and platform (Windows, Mac, and popular Linux distributions). The built wheels will be uploaded to PyPi, condaforce, and the releases section of our central GitHub repository.

The VFS support additions to OpenSim core (**WPB1**) will be packaged and distributed as part of OpenSim's existing packaging/distribution pipeline.

How the osimstud reference implementation (**WPB2/WPC1**) is packaged will depend on how it is implemented. The two most likely delivery mechanisms are to include it in the python bindings or in OpenSim core, which are outlined above.

10. What level of support will be provided for users of the software and how will this support be organised?

Users will be able to post technical issues to the GitHub repository page. Developers (in this project's team, or the general community) will then reproduce, test, and fix those issues. The amount of time our team provisions towards fixing issues will be dependent on a combination of the severity of the issue and how hard it is to fix it. Organizationally, we will intermittently reassess how much time we spend on fixing issues versus developing the work packages.

Users will also be able to post non-technical issues in a discussion forum or message the development team. Emails/messages will be lightly discouraged—the questions and answers are not findable—but, provided the question does not contain private information, we will rewrite and publish those questions online to grow a searchable knowledgebase of existing questions.

11. How do you plan to ensure long term maintenance of your software?

The plan fundamentally tackles long-term maintenance in two ways: by making other projects dependent on the work packages, and by architecting the work packages to require very little long-term maintenance to keep their as-delivered feature set working. This combination will ensure a “long tail” of sustained interest in the deliverables, which is paramount to ensuring their long-term maintenance by the community and future projects.

We have structured the plan to deliver an MVP early in the project (**WPA1**), followed by finding and encouraging other projects to collaborate on the development of the other work packages. Additionally, we are working on projects at TUD that are likely to benefit from the work packages, which will incentivize our core team to maintain the work packages long-term.

Section 6: References

1. <https://simtk.org/projects/opensim>
2. S. L. Delp *et al.*, "OpenSim: Open-Source Software to Create and Analyze Dynamic Simulations of Movement," in *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 54, no. 11, pp. 1940-1950, Nov. 2007, doi: [10.1109/TBME.2007.901024](https://doi.org/10.1109/TBME.2007.901024)
3. <https://opensimcreator.com>
4. <https://www.modelhealth.io/>

Section 7: Declaration

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I and all the individuals involved in this proposal satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands [Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) (The Universities of the Netherlands).
- The research organisation has been informed of this grant application and the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this programme.
- I have completed this application form truthfully.
- I have submitted a pre-proposal for this Call for proposals in ISAAC.